

Trukese

also known as “Chuuk”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Micronesia, Religion, Oceanic Religions

The Trukese are a group of people who inhabit what is now known as the Chuuk state of the Federated States of Micronesia. During the World War I era, Japan replaced Germany as the ruling power in Micronesia, and in 1945 the United States replaced Japan through a United Nations Trusteeship. Chuuk was incorporated as a state within the newly independent Federated States of Micronesia in 1986. This entry focuses more specifically on those living on the island of Romonum around the time of 1947. While this entry focuses on the traditional beliefs of the Trukese, it is important to note that Christian influence was present at this time. Traditional Trukese beliefs included various types of supernatural beings, rituals, and religious practitioners. Religious practitioners specialized in activities such as fortunetelling, mediumship, or leading specific rituals such as increasing breadfruit supply. Chiefs held authority, in part, due to a close connection with the supernatural realm. Because religious beliefs are tied up with the Trukese society at large, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself.

Date Range: 1912 CE - 1949 CE

Region: Romonum Island

Region tags: Oceania, Micronesia, Micronesia (Federated State of)

Romonum Island, Federated States of Micronesia, circa 1947

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=or19-002>

– Source 1 Description: Gladwin, T., & Sarason, S. B. (1953). *Truk: Man In Paradise*. Viking Fund Publications In Anthropology. New York: Wenner-Gren Foundation for Anthropological Research.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=or19-022>

– Source 2 Description: Bollig, L. (1927). *Inhabitants Of The Truk Islands: Religion, Life And A Short Grammar Of A Micronesian People*. Munster I W.: Aschendorff.

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=or19-000>

– Source 3 Description: Goodenough, W. H., & Skoggard, I. A. (1999). *Culture Summary: Chuuk*. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Both Catholic and Protestant missionaries have been working on Truk for over forty years and all but a few Trukese profess one or the other faith. How deeply this faith is held is open to conjecture" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:66).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– I don't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, the Trukese were pacified before the 25 year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, the Trukese were pacified before the 25 year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the Trukese recruit new members to their religious belief system.

Does the religion have official political support

Answer 'yes' also in cases where the religious and political spheres are not distinguished from one another, but the religious group's activities are tied up with, and supported by, the functioning of the society at large.

– No

Notes: The Trukese have no official political office to provide support to the religion; the Trukese have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, the traditional Trukese religious beliefs and practices were subject to Christian influence. "By the middle of the twentieth century all of Chuuk's people were at least nominally Christian, either Protestant or Catholic, and Christianity had become the focus of religious life" (Goodenough and Skoggard, 1999).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 230

Notes: "With an area of only slightly over a quarter of a square mile and a population of about 230, its [Romonum's] population density is close to 800 per square mile, which is much higher than any other island on Truk, though lower than that of many of the low islands to the south" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:68).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Because missionaries were gaining influence and followers on Romonum during the 20th century, it is difficult to determine what percentage of the population followed the traditional beliefs and practices, and what percentage of the population converted to Christianity.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "A district chiefship was divided between the oldest man in the senior female line in the chiefly lineage and the oldest man in the lineage generally... A chief's authority derived from two things. His lineage's ownership of the district's space entitled him to presentations of first fruits at stated times of the year. More importantly, it gave him authority over the conservation and use of the district's food resources. His authority also derived from his connection with the sky world, its gods, and their superhuman power to accomplish purposes. There was, therefore, a degree of sacredness associated with chiefs" (Goodenough and Skoggard, 1999).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

Hierarchy need not be formally institutionalized if it is widely recognized and accepted.

– No

Notes: The Trukese have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "[The chiefs] authority also derived from his connection with the sky world, its gods, and their superhuman power to accomplish purposes. There was, therefore, a degree of sacredness associated with chiefs" (Goodenough and Skoggard, 1999).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of monumental religious architecture (within the traditional religious group).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of monumental religious architecture (within the traditional religious group).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Human beings are believed to possess two souls, a good soul and a bad soul, which both survive the body after death. For a full description, see Bollig, 1927 pgs. 14-25.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "For the first few days after the burial the good and the bad souls of the deceased remain in the vicinity of the grave. The bad soul is what is usually referred to as the ghost, and remains indefinitely as a vague but not serious threat. The good soul stays with the body for three or four days, making occasional trips away, after which it is speeded on its way in a ceremony and goes to the lineage spirit canoe at an indefinite location, where it remains" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:166).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on the treatment of corpses.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Many dying persons determine the burial place themselves before death. They want to be buried on their own property so that they elli ellär pun, that is, may eat from their own ground...The dead are not infrequently buried in a house" (Bollig, 1927:18).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "At present all burials are made in a grave, with the body in a coffin usually made of imported but not necessarily good lumber" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:160).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of secondary burials.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "The relatives of the deceased are obliged to bring the own mönumä (death gift). The most varied things can be seen there, such as articles of clothing, pieces of cloth, aromatic oils, etc. The things are first put beside the dead and later wrapped up with the corpse and buried" (Bollig, 1927:17).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below and Bollig, 1927, pgs. 16-xx for a description of burial practices.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "Many dying persons determine the burial place themselves before death. They want to be buried on their own property so that they elli ellär pun, that is, may eat from their own ground...The dead are not infrequently buried in a house" (Bollig, 1927:18).

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: On personal property

Notes: "Many dying persons determine the burial place themselves before death. They want to be buried on their own property so that they elli ellär pun, that is, may eat from their own ground...The dead are not infrequently buried in a house" (Bollig, 1927:18).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Truk people think of the sky as inhabited by gods, and the earth, by spirits. Yet all these spirits come from Önulap and are subject to his leadership" (Bollig, 1927:12).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "Önulap is the highest of the gods. He is the father of the gods and human beings. Everything comes from him, including illness and misfortune. Everything is tinien Önulap (fate, messenger of the great spirit). Human beings too belong to Önulap" (Bollig, 1927:5).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Trukese.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Trukese.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Having everything go well is brought about by the protection of the önu [supernatural beings]; things go badly because of their inflicting punishment on human beings. Thus, everything adverse in the world is punishment for the violation of the commands or prohibitions which the önu, and especially Önulap, have imposed on human beings. The Truk people also say about disagreeable events: tinien Önulap, that is, decree of the 'Great Spirit.'" (Bollig, 1927:28).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Having everything go well is brought about by the protection of the önu [supernatural beings]; things go badly because of their inflicting punishment on human beings. Thus, everything adverse in the world is punishment for the violation of the commands or prohibitions which the önu, and especially Önulap, have imposed on h human beings. The Truk people also say about disagreeable events: tinien Önulap, that is, decree of the 'Great Spirit.'" (Bollig, 1927:28).

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [Note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas column 34], indicates that a high god is absent or not reported in substantial descriptions of religious beliefs (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The belief in ghosts, while strong, is rather poorly defined. They may be seen perhaps most commonly as simply a red spot of light at night, but on other occasions appear as clearly human figures. They may be identified as being the ghost of a particular relative or as the familiar spirit of a certain location, although still presumably the ghost of an actual person long dead" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:65).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "We saw earlier in this chapter the ghost of a recent ancestor punishing the lineage for its neglect of a pregnant mother by withholding her baby. The spirits of the dead are felt to have the function of watchdogs over the family solidarity; it is not entirely clear in fact whether the ghost that holds the baby is doing so on account of neglect of the mother only, or because the lineage members have generally been lax in their mutual obligations and this is a good opportunity (as it was phrased by one informant) to punish two members at once, mother and child. Again, then, we have a supernatural sanction for conformity" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "We saw earlier in this chapter the ghost of a recent ancestor punishing the lineage for its neglect of a pregnant mother by withholding her baby" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Besides Önulap, the Jupiter of the Truk people, there is still a large number of others, in part male, in part female, in part sympathetic, in part unsympathetic. The gods in their customs are often not a bit better than the Truk people themselves. They eat, drink, dance, play, marry, and also perform many a trick which is not at all appropriate for gods" (Bollig, 1927:7). "The Truk people think of the sky as inhabited by gods, and the earth, by spirits. Yet all these spirits come from Önulap and are subject to his leadership" (Bollig, 1927:12).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The majority of the nature spirits are not well-disposed toward human beings and try to do them harm wherever they can" (Bollig, 1927:29).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "Having everything go well is brought about by the protection of the önu [supernatural beings]; things go badly because of their inflicting punishment on human beings. Thus, everything adverse in the world is punishment for the violation of the commands or prohibitions which the önu, and especially Önulap, have imposed on human beings. The Truk people also say about disagreeable events: tinien Önulap, that is, decree of the 'Great Spirit.'" (Bollig, 1927:28).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Anyone who violates a binin [prohibition] incurs the penalty of the revenge of spirit concerned, the one that issued it. He becomes feienau. This is the punishment that the people of Truk abhor" (Bollig, 1927:41).

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "Each spirit has his binin [prohibition] which he imposes upon human beings. Most of these binin are food prohibitions...Anyone who violates a binin [prohibition] incurs the penalty of the revenge of spirit concerned, the one that issued it. He becomes feienau. This is the punishment that the people of Truk abhor" (Bollig, 1927:41).

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: "Each spirit has his binin [prohibition] which he imposes upon human beings. Most of these binin are food prohibitions...Anyone who violates a binin [prohibition] incurs the penalty of the revenge of spirit concerned, the one that issued it. He becomes feienau. This is the punishment that the people of Truk abhor" (Bollig, 1927:41).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Family solidarity

Notes: "We saw earlier in this chapter the ghost of a recent ancestor punishing the lineage for its neglect of a pregnant mother by withholding her baby. The spirits of the dead are felt to have the function of watchdogs over the family solidarity; it is not entirely clear in fact whether the ghost that holds the baby is doing so on account of neglect of the mother only, or because the lineage members have generally been lax in their mutual obligations and this is a good opportunity (as it was phrased by one informant) to punish two members at once, mother and child. Again, then, we have a supernatural sanction for conformity" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "Anyone who violates a binin [prohibition] incurs the penalty of the revenge of spirit concerned, the one that issued it. He becomes feienau. This is the punishment that the people of Truk abhor" (Bollig, 1927:41).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is metted out by many supernatural beings (Bollig, 1927:28, 41; Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Punishment is metted out by many supernatural beings (Bollig, 1927:28, 41; Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "We saw earlier in this chapter the ghost of a recent ancestor punishing the lineage for its neglect of a pregnant mother by withholding her baby. The spirits of the dead are felt to have the function of watchdogs over the family solidarity; it is not entirely clear in fact whether the ghost that holds the baby is doing so on account of neglect of the mother only, or because the lineage members have generally been lax in their mutual obligations and this is a good opportunity (as it was phrased by one informant) to punish two members at once, mother and child. Again, then, we have a supernatural sanction for conformity" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "We saw earlier in this chapter the ghost of a recent ancestor punishing the lineage for its neglect of a pregnant mother by withholding her baby. The spirits of the dead are felt to have the function of watchdogs over the family solidarity; it is not entirely clear in fact whether the ghost that holds the baby is doing so on account of neglect of the mother only, or because the lineage members have generally been lax in their mutual obligations and this is a good opportunity (as it was phrased by one informant) to punish two members at once, mother and child. Again, then, we have a supernatural sanction for conformity" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: "We saw earlier in this chapter the ghost of a recent ancestor punishing the lineage for its neglect of a pregnant mother by withholding her baby. The spirits of the dead are felt to have the function of watchdogs over the family solidarity; it is not entirely clear in fact whether the ghost that holds the baby is doing so on account of neglect of the mother only, or because the lineage members have generally been lax in their mutual obligations and this is a good opportunity (as it was phrased by one informant) to punish two members at once, mother and child. Again, then, we have a supernatural sanction for conformity" (Gladwin and Sarason, 1953:150).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that membership requires celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "The Truk natives are restrained by a number of binin (prohibitions). Not all binin are religious in character. Many are nothing but prohibitions by persons of higher position upon their subjects. The religious binin are usually designated as binin önu or binin ro. Each spirit has his binin which he imposes upon human beings. Most of these binin are food prohibitions. There is scarcely an edible fruit or an edible animal which does not come under the binin and is forbidden for certain circles. The extent of these binin is not always the same. Some apply only for certain periods, some forever. Some extend to individual persons, others over whole tribes" (Bollig, 1927:41).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– I don't know

Notes: "The prayer to the spirits is a daily custom of the Truk people. They appeal to the spirits in connection with eating, in connection with work, in sickness, and on the sea" (Bollig, 1927:33).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– I don't know

Notes: Large-scale rituals are present among the Trukese, such as dance ceremonies (see Bollig, 1927:194), but it is unclear if participation is mandatory.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

This question refers to the wider society in which the religious group is located.

– A tribe

Notes: The Trukese have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, according to Murdock and Wilson, (1972; Column 10: Descent) the Trukese have matrilineal descent with dispersed sibs. Further, the Trukese live in segmented communities with matrilineal sibs. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22. Because the Trukese have kin ties, the society is best described as a tribe.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Trukese have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery. Some police functions are assumed by the retainers of chiefs" (Column 10, Police; Retrieved from Tuden and Marshall, 1972).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community" (Column 9, Judiciary; Retrieved from Tuden and Marshall, 1972).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of institutionalized punishment.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "The main task of the chief is the laying down and execution of the buun fanu, that is, the tribal laws. In practice the buun is usually illusory, since nobody wants to follow it" (Bollig, 1927:126).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Trukese possess a calendar, but it is not of a religious nature. "The calendar of the Truk people has two annual seasons, räs, the breadfruit season, and äfän, the curcuma season, the northern trade season, which, of course, varies greatly...The year of the Truk people is a lunar year and has 12 months (maram)" (Bollig, 1927:227).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Trukese rely on agriculture (horticulture) and fishing for subsistence. Source of information

from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Trukese rely on agriculture (horticulture) and fishing for subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.